

THE ROLE OF "INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE" IN TEACHING LANGUAGES

Zulfizar Karimova

Senior teacher, Tashkent branch of MSU named after M. V. Lomonosov

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10011449>

One of the purposes of teaching language is to enable learners to establish good human relationship and cultural pluralism in literature, history, art, and other fields of science. It is the key topic of the globalization where the discussion on cultural pluralism take place. In the spirit of cultural pluralism, all American newspapers try to show diversity of the US life taking into consideration WASP, Afro- and Latin American traditions. Analysis of online materials (news, reports, analytical articles, journalists' blogs) of the three leading American newspapers: The New York Times, The Wall Street Journal illustrates that language reflects the environment in which we live. In addition to the environment, language reflects cultural values.

At the end of the 90s, the concept of "intercultural competence" as an indicator of a person's formed ability to effectively participate in intercultural communication and as an important category of a new scientific theory entered the Russian methodology. The appeal to the new scientific theory in linguistics is conditioned by a number of objective circumstances.

Modern geo-economic and geo-cultural situations force a person to be able to coexist in a common life world, that is, to be able to build a mutually beneficial dialog with all subjects of this common life space, to be able to build humanitarian intercultural bridges between representatives of different professions and cultures [1]. An important role in this is played by language, which is the only possible tool through which the interaction between people of different nations and cultures becomes a reality. Hence, the reorientation of linguodidactic and methodological research on the problem of intercultural communication, and, more precisely, on the problems of forming students' ability to effectively participate in it.

Intercultural communication is interpreted by Russian linguodidacticians as a set of specific processes of interaction between communication partners belonging to different linguistic and ethno-cultural communities.

Communication in intercultural situations, even if its participants possess a common language code, is always characterized by conflicts between knowledge and ignorance.

The main vector of modern linguodidactic and methodical scientific research should be aimed at resolving these conflicts, i.e. at theoretical substantiation of the most optimal ways to develop students' ability to realize and understand foreign lexico-grammatical constructions corresponding to the norms of communicative activity of an individual of a different linguo-ethno-cultural community and a different national-linguistic picture of the world. It is about the formation of a person's ability to intercultural communication. This process is carried out in educational conditions in the interrelation of the students' mastering of the foreign language code, development of their cultural experience, which includes the individual's attitude to himself, to the world. Mastering each new language, a person expands not only his horizons, but also the boundaries of his worldview and worldview. The way he perceives the world and what he sees in it is always reflected in the concepts formed on the basis of the person of the original language and taking into account the variety of expressive means inherent in this language [2]. Moreover, no situations are perceived by man impartially. They are evaluated by him, as well as phenomena of other cultures, always through the prism of cultural norms and values accepted in the native linguosociety, through the prism of the model of worldview internalized by the

individual. In these conditions, intercultural relations are formed between people, in which cultural systemicity is cognized in the moments of transcending the boundaries of the system.

Culture is not only present in the classroom setting but also in the language that is being taught. It is important to become good observers of the culture in order to be able to use the language well. Students are to be equipped with the cognitive skills they need in a second-culture environment. The cultural variables need to be respected if the students are to benefit from new experiences, to escape cross-cultural misunderstandings – conflicts of values and expectations. Learners need to know not only the linguistic knowledge but also the culturally acceptable ways of interacting with others. It permits entrance into contact with other realities and cultures, to understand their mentality and varied customs, creates cultural understanding, which is the key to a tolerance, respect, consensus [3]. One of the key components of communicative competence is discourse competence. Discourse competence presupposes an ability to recognize the communicative purpose of a given genre. Indeed if one has misunderstood the nature of genre, communication will fail, irrespective of one’s linguistic ability. Cultural literacy is necessary in order to understand the language being used. If we select language without being aware of the cultural implication, we may not communicate well. Communicating with non-native speakers in any language takes skill, experience, and sensitivity.

Skills and abilities, cognition and skills, the development of links in one chain - the formation of personality. The teaching foreign language in the context of intercultural theory has a great personal-developmental potential and from this point of view is promising for the school. The main conclusion of the above is summarized in the understanding of the modern purpose of language learning as an interactive whole, which has an "output" on the learner's personality, on his/her readiness, abilities and personal qualities, allowing him/her to carry out various types of speech-thought activity in the conditions of social interaction with representatives of other linguoethno-societies and their culture of a different linguistic image of the world.

The integrity of this goal is manifested in the interrelation of its three aspects: pragmatic, cognitive, pedagogical.

- The pragmatic aspect is connected with the formation of communicative competence in the learner;

- Cognitive (cognitive) aspect - with the use of the language as a tool for learning another linguistic culture and means of developing intercultural competence and personality in general.

- Pedagogical aspect - determines the way of extra-linguistic existence of a multicultural linguistic personality. The extra-linguistic qualities of a personality capable of successfully communicating in situations of intercultural interaction also include independence, activity, empathy [4].

Getting to know another culture, Building tolerance and academic honesty through English teaching – these are topical issues of today to support and develop the civilizations’ dialog. The more you know about the verbal customs of your particular partner, the more successful your intercultural communication will be. The cultural priorities motivate people to behave in certain ways.

Diversity is a fact, and it is not going away. Not all cultures in the world are going to become like ours.

Most people in the world actually think we ought to try to imitate and adopt their cultures. This is true no matter who “we” and “they” are. Somehow we need to learn “to accept

the fact that there are many roads to truth and no culture has a corner on the path or is better equipped than others to search for it”.

The principle of surviving in a multicultural world is that one does not need to think, feel, and act in the same way in order to agree on practical issues and to cooperate. We can agree to be different and to allow for diversity. We can celebrate our own culture in terms of how it is or is not like another, and celebrate other cultures because they are different or are not. The more we know about other cultures the more we will know about our own.

If you work for a foreign firm, your decision about which language to study will be influenced by where your company does business. Being able to speak the partner’s language also carries symbolic value. If you do business with a firm in Quebec, you may get through on English, but you send more positive signals if you are able to speak French. Communicating with non-native speakers in any language takes skill, experience, and sensitivity[5].

The first approach is linguo-ethno-economic - it is aimed at students' realization of the importance and necessity of knowing their native language and culture, their belonging to a certain ethnos. For Russia, polylingual-ethno-cultural teaching consists in directing public consciousness to preserve the ethnic identity of all peoples inhabiting the country, to form at the individual level of consciousness a sense of ethno-psychological, not only political belonging to an interethnic community.

The native linguo-ethno-culture should occupy an essential place in the learning process. This process should be aimed at forming an understanding of the linguoethno-cultural specifics of the native speaker of the target language while preserving the natural style of communication, which is intended to distinguish his/her speech and non-speech behavior in intercultural communication with foreign peers. Domestic scientists have yet to select culturological samples to be offered at the lesson. It is already evident that the intercultural component of the learning process necessitates the search for new psychological, pedagogical and methodological solutions.

These solutions are related to the modeling of language learning systems as a process of acquiring individual experience of communicating with a foreign linguoculture. Students, comparing different conceptual systems, enrich their consciousness by internationalizing the world outside their native cultural reality and means of structuring it.

REFERENCES

1. Fusco Girard, L. The role of cultural urban landscape towards a new urban economics: New structural assets for increasing economic productivity through hybrid processes. *Hous. Policies Urban Econ.* 2014, 1, 3–27.
2. Srakar, A.; Vecco, M. Culture as a Fourth Dimension of Sustainable Development? A Statistical Analysis. 2016. Available online: http://eventos.uva.es/file_manager/get_paper/3421 (accessed on 12 October 2017)
3. Lo Bianco, J., Liddicoat, A. & Crozet, C. (eds.) 1999, *Striving for the Third Place: Intercultural Competence through Language Education*. Melbourne: Language Australia.
4. Vescio, T. K., Gervais, S. J., Heiphetz, L., & Bloodhart, B. (2014). The stereotypic behaviors of the powerful and their effect on the relatively powerless (pp. 247–266), in T. D. Nelson (Ed), *Handbook of prejudice, stereotyping and discrimination*. New York: Psychology Press.

5. Cummins, J (2013). Language and Identity in multilingual schools: Constructing evidence-based instructional policies. in D Little, C Leung and P van Avermaet (eds.) *Managing Diversity in Education: Languages, Policies, Pedagogies*.